

Informatio hypothesis - a potential supplement to cell theory

Savani Anbalagan^{1,2}

¹Institute of Molecular Biology and Biotechnology, Faculty of Biology, Adam Mickiewicz University, Poznań, Poland.

²Correspondence

E-mail: savani.anbalagan@amu.edu.pl

Tel: +48 61 829 5905

Running title: Informatio hypothesis

Keywords: cell theory, gasocrine hypothesis, circumcentium hypothesis, environment

For reasons that remain unclear, despite roughly 4 billion years of cellular evolution, cell theory has only three well-accepted postulates¹. I previously proposed the gasocrine and circumiacentium hypotheses, which state that all cells require gasocrine signaling² and are limited by their environment³, respectively. These hypotheses can also be considered from an information-based perspective, not only between or across cells, but also in relation to the environment. I propose the hypothesis, "**All cells pass information**". A simple falsification experiment would be to find a cell that cannot pass any information, (e.g., A living, dead or decomposing cell that cannot release any of the currently known signaling molecules or factors). Thus, this hypothesis is a potential supplement to cell theory.

REFERENCES

1. Hyllner J, Mason C, Wilmut I. Cells: from Robert Hooke to cell therapy—a 350 year journey. *Philos Trans R Soc Lond B Biol Sci* 2015; 370:20150320.
2. Anbalagan S. Gasocrine hypothesis - a potential supplement to cell theory. *Acta Biochim Pol* 2025; 72:15465.
3. Anbalagan S. Circumiacentium hypothesis - a potential supplement to cell theory. Zenodo 2026.